

Test Anxiety and Interventions for ... (Akpeji and Dane, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10687700>

Test Anxiety and Interventions for Mental Health and Improvement in Learning Outcome among Secondary School Students in Nigeria: Implication for Counselling

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Abstract

The paper analysed past reviews regarding test anxiety as it affects students in their learning outcome. The purpose of this paper is to give a qualitative analysis of test anxiety and its interventions for mental health and improvement in learning outcome among secondary school students. The paper also identified causes of test anxiety and coping strategies for test anxiety. The paper noted that it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that test anxiety is common among students but it varies in degrees. For some students' it may be beneficial, for others it may lead to poor academic performance and may cause negative effect on their wellness. It further states that for a person to be seen as adjusted to test anxiety issues his/her state of mind as well as general mental health should be seen to be stable and the individual should be able to effectively make use of his/her capacity by showing psychological reliance in taking personal and social adjustments to meet with the ever-changing environment within which he/she co-exist. The paper suggest that teachers and other stakeholders involved in the process of educating the students should emphasize on the importance of holistic preparation for test, in order to prevent the negative effects of test anxiety and ensure a stable physical and mental health in their process of learning.

Keywords: Test Anxiety, Mental Health, Interventions, Students and Counselling.

Introduction

Anxiety is a typical occurrence that establishes a cause of poor academic performance among students. Anxiety leads to self-preoccupation which is manifested as self-minimization and results in negative cognitive assessment, lack of focus, negative physiological reactions, mental health problems and academic setback. Anxiety has its origin in early childhood with both developmental and environmental elements; these elements are all connected to perceived feelings of insecurity and inadequacy that are conveyed into adulthood. Anxiety is also viewed as a reoccurring effect of tension resulting from anticipated necessity. Atsehe, Kwaghgbah, Iorlumun and Agbecha, (2022) noted that anxiety is a state of uneasiness, worry or feeling of uncertainty about impending or on-going programmes, examinations or tests. Cognitive performance and information processing may be critically affected by anxiety. Anxiety is one of the emotional components of a person's life. Every task performance to an extent is accomplished by some measures of anxiety. Anxiety as a collection of physiological and cognitive reactions forms disturbances, fear of failure and stomach discomfort. It is a menace that has eaten deep into the fabric of student's life and at the same time, become an obstacle to their progress. (Agbor, Chile & Ruth, 2020).

Anxiety was defined by Bethel-Eke, and Ikpa, (2017) as the experiencing of an undesirable and unclear like feeling, which the individual predicts a negative outcome of an activity. The extreme level of anxiety impairs an individual's mental and physical health and also has a negative effect on the persons, social, occupational, and educational performance. Anxiety can be divided into two categories: state anxiety and trait anxiety. The trait anxiety is described as the individual's capability to perceive different situations from the environment like danger and threat. On the other hand, state anxiety is described as the perception of individual's emotional situation. State anxiety is also seen as a transient response to stress that consist of subjective feeling of worry, nervousness, apprehension, tension and arousal of autonomic nervous system (Sudheer & Naachimuthu, 2022).

In recent years "test anxiety" has evolved with different variety of definitions and different researchers have given their views of the concept which has increased the needed knowledge of the concept. Test anxiety is grouped under a category

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of anxious states and negative emotions that are often linked with neuroticism. Owens-Sogolo, (2021) explains that test anxiety is often developed out of fear of negative evaluation, it is comparable to social phobia, which causes fears of being negatively judged and these might lead to students spending more of their time worrying about the outcome of an expected test and how others will judge their performance than on the test itself. It is also feeling of worry, apprehension, nervousness or uneasiness that occurs when a student encounters test or examination in any form and at any level (Balogun, Balogun & Onyencho, 2017). Biologically individual's genetic makeup predisposes them to react differently to anxiety provoking situations. The environment a person belongs to may also play a role in contributing to the reaction to stimuli. Getting used to exam phobia due to negative perception which is associated with failure, will bring about different levels of anxiety in different individuals. In most situations it is expected that students' levels of test anxiety will increase during the examination period as compared to other school activities. Koramoah, Dzakadzie and Danyoh, (2022) explained that a little anxiety during exams is required which will help students to get motivated and learn. Mounting up so much of anxiety will not help the student to perform, rather it will influence the academic performance negatively. Some of the psychological symptoms that build up in students before a test include difficulty in concentrating, restlessness, insomnia, fatigue, abdominal pain among others.

Test anxiety has induced an unfavorable condition which constitutes intense fear of test situations which affects the mental health of the individual. Students who experience high level of test anxiety are more likely to perform poorly academically. Persistent test anxiety is associated with low academic performance. The need for the study of students is warranted, because of the disturbing cases of poor academic performance in schools (Balogun, Balogun & Onyencho, 2017). Mental health can be seen as a state of mind of an individual that can effectively make use of his or her capacity by showing psychological reliance in taking personal and social adjustments to meet with the ever-changing environment within which he or she co-exist with people (Eze & Mgbenkemdi, 2019). Student's test anxiety is one of the biggest problems that affect the mental health which in most cases is seen as the reason for poor academic performance. The need for strategies for lifelong adjustment have been noted over the years by stakeholders in the education sector as one of the most viable options for student's positive performance expectations. Students are often expected to study hard and improve their study habits. Even if classes are larger, instructors should have different teaching techniques, which could help them still pay attention to those who need them in solving their anxiety issues (Galle, Atiku & Bala, 2020).

The fear of one's ability to do well in a testing situation is one of the main reasons for students experiencing anxiety. Anxiety prevents students from showing the most of their ability on examination. This is because students in most cases have phobia for examinations. Examination anxiety comes with various symptoms; that include insomnia, lack of appetite and lack of concentration (Tambaya, 2019). Bentil, Donkor, Oti, and Adzifome, (2020). Investigated the factors that trigger test anxiety while using coping strategies needed to reduce anxiety among Junior High School students in the Effutu Municipality. The investigations employed the cross-sectional descriptive survey design with quantitative approach where through proportionate stratified random sampling was carried out, a sample of 746 students was obtained from both public and private Junior High Schools in the three (3) circuits of the Effutu Municipality. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study revealed that even though different kinds of factors trigger test and examination anxiety amongst the students, lack of self-esteem was the most contributory factor while subject load of the students shows the least influence on test anxiety. The study further established that good study habits as well as skills, effective teacher support, motivation, reduction of students' workload, updating curricular activities, and having enough resting and sleeping time were the coping strategies to be employed to reduce test anxiety. Additionally, it was found that factors such as having low self-confidence, past experience and beliefs about test, history of consistent poor academic performance, subject load, and psychological factors jointly contributed significantly to test anxiety among students. Besides, motivation of students, reduction of subject load and good teachers support for students were the coping strategies needed to manage examination anxiety. Based on these results, it was recommended that regular educational programmes such as symposia and school festivals should be conducted to heighten students' self-esteem, and remove negative past experiences and beliefs about test while exploring other coping strategies to reduce test anxiety for better academic performance.

Causes of Anxiety

Anxiety is the experience of feeling anxious from time to time as well as nervousness and thudding of a person's heart, the shortness of breath, and the mind going places within the person's mind without control. Despite some negative attributes of anxiety, it can also be seen as a big contributor of us staying alive as human beings because it helps us not to take things for granted. The early exposure to stress and the experience of trauma are substantial risk factors for anxiety disorders. Anxiety has biological causes, such as issues with the regulation of neurotransmitters and heritable genetic causes (Smoller, 2016; Milne

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& Munro 2020). The ability to relate to a person who experiences anxiety is a crucial part of a therapeutic relationship and, as such, it is crucial to acknowledge that anxiety is not ‘just’ a mental state but also has physiological causes and responses, which can be frightening (Milne & Munro 2020). A recent review identified that there is a genetic heritability of around 30% for GAD and that the same predisposing genes are present across sexes (Gottschalk & Domschke, 2017; Milne & Munro 2020). Pro-inflammatory markers have also been shown to directly modulate affective behaviour and heightened concentrations of inflammatory signals have been described in GAD, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), panic disorder and phobias (Milne & Munro 2020). Exposure to stress has been linked to anxiety, as well as having a negative impact on the body’s immune, cardiovascular, neuroendocrine and central nervous systems (Khan & Khan, 2017; Milne & Munro 2020). Physical health problems can also cause anxiety disorders, in some people with a malignant disease, for example, a response of anxiety is understandable however, in other individuals, anxiety may increase to an extreme level, if it does not improve.

Test anxiety is a common phenomenon among students, and anxiety disorders are increasingly prevalent among them (Milne & Chakraborty, 2023). Studies also have suggested that older students tend to experience more stress than younger students, and female students have a higher likelihood of experiencing anxiety than male students (Milne & Chakraborty, 2023). Tertiary students are seen to encounter different challenges, such as adapting to new environments that can alter their routines and habits. Additionally, there is an increased demand for academic success. These emotions can have adverse effects on their academic performance, subsequently causing heightened levels of stress, depression, and anxiety (Milne & Chakraborty, 2023). Research has determined the effects of test anxiety on academic outcomes, given that this phenomenon stems from various sources. Numerous studies have ventured into the complex interplay between psychological, physiological, and environmental factors that contribute to the onset of test anxiety, and how it can impair students' ability to perform at their optimal. Different studies have suggested that inadequate preparation may be the underlying cause of test anxiety in students. It has also been postulated that the fear of poor performance or failing to meet one's own or others' expectations can cause a vicious cycle of anxiety, leading to decreased motivation and increased negative self-talk. Such disturbing thought patterns can further escalate the feeling of poor preparation, creating feedback that can in great measure hamper students' test-taking abilities (Chakraborty, 2023).

According to Naveh-Benjamin, Craik, Guez and Dori as cited in Chakraborty, (2023), highly test-anxious students exhibit lower aptitude in organising the material to be learned in contrast to their less anxious peers. Their research has shed light on the pivotal role of anxiety in impeding students' cognitive processing and information retrieval. Individuals experiencing high levels of test anxiety tend to experience cognitive overload, which can impair their ability to spot critical information from irrelevant information, organise it effectively, and integrate it into their existing knowledge base. As a result, test-anxious students may struggle to perform well on tests, leading to a vicious cycle of anxiety, poor performance, and decreased self-confidence. Several research studies have consistently noted that students with high levels of test anxiety tend to have suboptimal academic behaviors in contrast to their less anxious counterparts (Chakraborty, 2023). This observation is further corroborated by Hembree as cited in Chakraborty, (2023), which postulated that ineffective study skills can contribute to poor academic performance, leading to heightened anxiety levels during subsequent examinations.

Interventions for Test Anxiety

Anyone who faces test or exam anxiety is vulnerable to the negative impact on their test or exams and mental health. The need for effective interventions of test anxiety for lifelong adjustments of students cannot be over emphasized. Majority of interventions focuses on increasing cognitive restructuring. Nevertheless, most practical interventions focus on improving the whole picture of an individual's test-taking behaviors. Test-anxious students can learn several cognitive behavioral techniques, such as fighting irrational beliefs with self-reinforcing statements, self-instruction, and coping strategies when faced with the sensation of anxiety. The major goal of cognitive behavioral interventions for anxiety is to help the students recognize irrational or maladaptive thoughts and replace those thoughts with more realistic versions of the initial perception. Grouping of the various methods students have in approaching learning tasks. Dodgson in Ossai (2012) grouped these methods to include the utilization of those procedures known as “SQ3R” and others. The SQ3R method includes a series of five steps designated by the initials S-Q-R-R-R. The first step “S” that is to be employed is the survey of the material by reading the parts of the chapter that gives an overview of the topics covered. The next step is the “Q” in SQ3R which stands for question. Formulate a question either aloud or in writing-before actually reading a section of the material. The following step “R” is to read the materials. This involves reading carefully and even more importantly, reading actively and critically. The next step is the second “R” which stands for ‘recite’ meaning to recite what is been read and describe to one or ones reading partner. The final “R”

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refers to review. This will involve looking over the information and re-reading the features in one's textbook that provide one with an overview of the chapter.

Coping and life adjustment strategies for test anxiety

Test Anxiety is common and disabling. Today it seems more and more often students experience anxiety. If you suffer from test anxiety, there are a number of coping strategies that you can employ. Below are some tips to help you cope.

1. Preparing well for your test can help reduce test anxiety. First, make sure you have done all you have to do in terms of preparation. Cramming for a test or exam will only increase anxiety, so give yourself enough time to learn your materials well.
2. Always being negative of one's self can worsen test anxiety. When performance suffers because of test anxiety, it can be easy to fall into a downward spiral of negative thinking. Check what you say to yourself and replace any negative thoughts with positive ones.
3. Some thoughts are not helpful such as I should have prepared more than I did, I must be an unfortunate person and I have to do well, everything is on the line. It is better to tell yourself positive things like I am prepared for this test, I am smart enough to do well and Even if I don't do well, it's not the end of the world.
4. It is important you arrive early for your exam to reduce anxiety. Nothing will heighten anxiety like the feeling of rushing to get to a test. Arrive at least few minutes early. If waiting for the test to begin makes you nervous, revise your notes to keep your mind occupied. Avoid people who are anxious before a test and do not second guess what you know.
5. Make use of relaxation strategies such as muscle relaxation and take your imagination off negative things as well as control rapid breathing. Use these strategies in the weeks leading up to a test, and during the testing situation as needed.
6. Maintain focus and stay away from distractions during a test. During the test, do everything you can to avoid talking or answering anybody. Remember to take your time but check your watch to pace yourself. Before starting the test, do a quick review and read directions twice. Start with the easiest questions first.
7. Accept that you can accommodate little test anxiety. Recognize that a little bit of anxiety before a test is a good thing. If you did not feel nervous at all, you might not be motivated to do your best. It is only when anxiety becomes hard to manage that it is a problem.
8. Gratify yourself for overcoming your test anxiety. Plan a reward for yourself after the test. Take some time to enjoy yourself and clear your mind. Do not dwell on mistakes you may have made or worry about whether you did well or not. Whenever possible, give yourself a break before studying for another test.

Counselling Implication

Counselling encourages the use of therapeutic approach in handling problems that affect clients. Based on this, the therapeutic approaches that can be used in reducing academic anxiety are behavioral therapy (BT), cognitive therapy (CT), and cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT). BT, such as systematic desensitization or applied relaxation, principally intervening in the somatic symptoms of test anxiety, whilst CT, such as rational-emotive therapy or schema-based therapy, which is used to treat cognitive beliefs and structures for modification. CBT combine's treatment principles from both BT and CT approaches (Huntley, Young, Jha, & Fisher, 2019). CBT intend to discover and modify the client's thinking patterns that are associated with anxiety and worrying feelings. This type of treatment has two main parts: a cognitive part made to limit distorted thinking and a behavioral part designed to change the way people react to the objects or situations that trigger anxiety. For example, a client receiving cognitive-behavioral therapy for anxiety disorder might work on learning that experiencing panic attacks does not mean that one's heart is failing.

CBT assist people faced with their fears and try to help them become desensitized to anxiety-triggering situations. Psychotherapy is another treatment of counselling for anxiety disorders. It involves a client talking to a trained mental health professional, psychiatrist, psychologist, or counsellor. Sessions may explore the causes of anxiety and possible ways to deal with symptoms. The intent of CBT is to help the client or counselee think more positively about life and free himself from unhelpful patterns of behaviour. CBT deals with current situations more than events in client's past or childhood. CBT has been shown to work for a variety of mental health problems. In particular, CBT can help with: depression, anxiety, panic attacks, phobias, obsessive compulsive disorder and so on.

Huntley, Young, Jha, & Fisher, (2019) Explained that there are two main forms of educational intervention for test anxiety; 'Test-wiseness' training that focuses on the skills needed to take an examination (e.g. surveying a written test to know

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which questions are given greater marks and so require more time and attention) and study skills training that focuses on ways of learning and encoding material in the most optimal way e.g. more emphasis on deeper levels of processing of to-be-learned material and less emphasis on rote memorization.

Conclusion

The paper concludes that it is normal for students to have test anxiety that helps them prepare themselves for a test, on the other hand it also states that uncontrollable test anxiety can also negatively disturb the students and affect them physically, emotionally, as well as cognitively and can result in poor test performance. It further states that for a person to be seen as adjusted to test anxiety issues his/her state of mind and general mental health should be seen to effectively make use of his/her capacity by showing psychological reliance in taking personal and social adjustments to meet with the ever-changing environment within which he/she co-exist. The study affirms that major causes of test anxiety among students are high grades expectations, phobia for failing and judgment of their academic performance by others which in turn negatively affects the outcome of their test.

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